

EFFECT OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND CREATIVITY ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

The present study was conducted to explore the relationship between emotional intelligence and Creativity on the academic achievement of Secondary School Students. Emotional Intelligence (EI) refers to the ability to recognize, understand, and manage both one's own emotions and the emotions of others. It involves skills that enable individuals to navigate social interactions, communicate effectively, empathize with others, resolve conflicts, and make informed decisions based on emotional cues. Creativity generates novel ideas, solutions, or valuable and original concepts. It involves thinking outside the box, breaking from conventional patterns, and approaching problems from new perspectives. Creativity is not limited to the arts; it permeates all aspects of human endeavor, from science and technology to business and everyday problem-solving. The main focus of the present research is to determine the Effect of Emotional Intelligence and Creativity on the academic achievement of secondary school students. The population includes all the secondary school students of Davangere City. The sample consists of 100 secondary school students from Davangere City, Karnataka. The present research paper aims to study the objectives of the Effect of Emotional Intelligence and Creativity on the academic achievement of secondary school students with prime aims (1) To prepare and develop the Emotional Intelligence and Creativity program for secondary school students. (2) To determine the effectiveness of the Emotional Intelligence and Creativity program for secondary school students. This study was completed using an experimental research method based on a pre-test and post-test research approach.

Key Words: Academic Achievement, Creativity, Emotional Intelligence

Introduction:

Education is a continuous, systematic, and planned process. It is the development of the potential of a being to its maximum by the harmonious growth of the physical, mental, social, emotional, and spiritual. Emotional Intelligence (EI) refers to the ability to recognize, understand, and manage both one's own emotions and the emotions of others. It involves skills that enable individuals to navigate social interactions, communicate effectively, empathize with others, resolve conflicts, and make informed decisions based on emotional cues. Creativity

generates novel ideas, solutions, or concepts that are valuable and original. It involves thinking outside the box, breaking from conventional patterns, and approaching problems from new perspectives. Creativity is not limited to the arts; it permeates all aspects of human endeavor, from science and technology to business and everyday problem-solving.

▪ **There are several components to Emotional Intelligence:**

1. **Self-awareness:** This involves recognizing and understanding one's own emotions, as well as their impact on thoughts, behavior, and interactions with others.
2. **Self-regulation:** This component involves managing and regulating one's emotions appropriately. It includes impulse control, adaptability, and coping with stress and frustration effectively.
3. **Motivation:** Emotional intelligence also involves being driven by personal goals, having a passion for work, and being able to delay gratification in pursuit of long-term objectives.
4. **Empathy:** Empathy is the ability to understand and share the feelings of others. It involves perspective-taking, recognizing others' emotions, responding compassionately, and understanding.
5. **Social skills:** This component involves the ability to build and maintain relationships, communicate effectively, influence others, and resolve conflicts constructively. It also includes skills such as leadership, teamwork, and networking.

Emotional intelligence is considered crucial for personal and professional success. Individuals with high emotional intelligence are often better able to navigate social situations, build strong relationships, and achieve their goals. Moreover, research has shown that emotional intelligence is correlated with various positive outcomes, including improved mental health, job performance, and leadership effectiveness. Therefore, developing emotional intelligence skills can benefit personal and professional growth.

▪ **Key components of Creativity Include:**

1. **Originality:** Creating something new and unique, whether it's a piece of art, a scientific theory, or a business strategy.
2. **Fluency:** Generating a large quantity of ideas or solutions, even if many of them are unconventional or impractical.
3. **Flexibility:** Being able to shift between different modes of thinking, adapt to new information, and explore multiple possibilities.

4. **Elaboration:** Developing and refining ideas or concepts through experimentation, iteration, and collaboration.
5. **Problem-solving:** Using creative thinking to overcome obstacles, find innovative solutions, and address complex challenges.

Cultivating Creativity involves brainstorming, mind mapping, lateral thinking exercises, and exposure to diverse perspectives and experiences. It also requires openness to risk, failure, and uncertainty, often inherent aspects of the creative process. Ultimately, Creativity thrives in environments that encourage curiosity, exploration, and the freedom to explore unconventional ideas.

- **Significance of the Study:**

The present research allows the learner to express their thoughts adequately. The Emotional Intelligence and Creativity on Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students program helps students raise influential citizens. The program promotes effective learning and underpins continuous personal, social, moral, and economic improvement. A program is essential for developing critical thinking and making independent learners. This study helps develop qualities and helps learners get involved in society.

This research enables the learners to invent and construct new ideas to understand the positive attitude toward sustainability. This study is important to help the students make decisions and develop their knowledge through their experiences.

The present study is important for finding various self-learning strategies to understand well-being. It also helps the teachers create a learning environment to support and challenge the learner's thinking and invest in individual capability and self-responsibility.

Objectives:

1. To prepare and develop the Emotional Intelligence and Creativity program for secondary school students.
2. To determine the effectiveness of the Emotional Intelligence and Creativity program for secondary school students.

- **Population and Sample:**

The population for the present research study consists of all the secondary school students of Davangere City.

- **Sample and Sampling Method:**

The sample for this present research study consists of 100 secondary school students of Davangere City, Karnataka, selected for experimentation by incidental sampling.

▪ **Hypothesis:**

Research Hypothesis: There will be a significant difference between the mean score of pre-test and post-test of secondary school students of Davangere City, Karnataka, taught by the Emotional Intelligence and Creativity Program.

Null Hypothesis: There will be no significant difference between the mean score of the pre-test and post-test of secondary school students of Davangere City, Karnataka, taught by the Emotional Intelligence and Creativity Program.

▪ **Variables:**

1. **Dependent Variable:** The dependent variable for the present research study is the academic achievement of secondary school students.
2. **Independent Variables:** The independent variables for the present research study are the Emotional Intelligence and Creativity Program.

▪ **Review of Related Literature:**

The reviews of related literature aim to provide previous studies and information concerned with the research problems. The researcher studied and reviewed Emotional Intelligence and Creativity related books, magazines, articles, and online sources for the present study. The researcher also reviews previous theses, dissertations, and the same research-based projects related to Emotional Intelligence and Creativity. Many studies have shown a positive correlation between EI and academic success. Students with higher EI tend to perform better academically. EI skills such as self-regulation, empathy, and social skills are linked to improved learning outcomes and classroom behavior. A few studies revealed that students who exhibit creativity are often more engaged in learning and can approach problems from multiple perspectives, leading to better academic performance.

Research Procedure: Researcher finalized the following Research Procedure:

The researcher identified the problem-related present scenario. After selecting the problem, the researcher reviewed the related literature and previous research. According to the topic, the researcher finalized the objectives and constructed the hypothesis for the study. The researcher selected the sample and sampling method for the present study. A pre-test program and a post-test were conducted for the same study. The statistical techniques Mean, SD, and 't' tests were used for the data analysis. As per data analysis, the researcher finds observations and major findings that meet the objectives.

▪ **Tools and Methods: Techniques, Procedure followed:** Experimental Method:

1. Single Group Design.
2. Pre-test- Post-test

The researcher prepared some strategies for Value Based Education Program:

1. Emotional Intelligence and Creativity related Lecture Series
2. Emotional Intelligence and Creativity related Group Work
3. One week activities: Theme- Emotional Intelligence and Creativity
4. Barin Storming and Problem Solving Program (BSPSP) Implementation

▪ **Results:**

• **Data Analysis:**

The researcher prepared 20 Multiple Choice Questions on pre-test and post-test for secondary school students. The researcher prepared and developed the Emotional Intelligence and Creativity for secondary school students. After implementing the program, the researcher conducted a post-test for the same respondents. Finally, the researcher analyzed the data and found the same observations.

Statistical Tool	Pre-test	Post-test	Obtained 't' Value		Calculated 't' Value
			0.05 level	0.01 level	
Mean	10.36	12.50	2.05	2.76	4.20*
SD	3.57	3.77			
R	0.70				

* Rejected at 0.01 and 0.05 significance level

Graphical Representation of Pre-test & Post-test Mean, SD

- **Interpretation:**

The calculated 't' value is 4.20, which exceeds the observed 't' table value at 0.01 and 0.05; the significance level is 2.76 and 2.05, respectively.

It shows that the obtained value $t = 4.20$ results from the treatment of the Emotional Intelligence and Creativity program given by the researcher. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the research hypothesis is accepted.

- **Findings:**

From the above interpretation of data, it was observed that the Emotional Intelligence and Creativity Program for secondary school students, which the researcher prepared, was effective.

Conclusions: Emotional Intelligence and Creativity Program is the ideal way of thinking and acting in a society. Emotional intelligence and creativity are the ways of positive thinking and behavior in an ideal society. Emotional intelligence and creativity are about understanding and explaining the extremely complex nature of values in national and global settings. Emotional Intelligence and Creativity is the healthy way is the most important condition to build a peaceful society and the world.

1. The conclusion of the study is based on the following points.
2. Learners were able to construct their understanding.
3. Teachers were able to create a program to improve the drawbacks.
4. The learners improved their skills in the real world.

The Emotional Intelligence and Creativity Program played an important role in the overall development of secondary school students. Now, it is expected to help positive awareness and develop self-confidence. The Emotional Intelligence and Creativity Program played a significant role in better development.

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